

From Conventional to Technological Learning Experience: Cambodian Undergraduate EFL Students' Perceptions of Electronic Books on Extensive Reading Practices

Rachana Thav

Internal Quality Assurance Office, National University of Battambang, Cambodia

Nangsamith Each

Internal Quality Assurance Office, National University of Battambang, Cambodia

Abstract

The proliferation of electronic books (e-books) has significantly transformed reading practices, offering new paths for language learning, especially extensive reading (ER). This study investigated the perceptions of Cambodian undergraduate EFL students regarding ER using e-books, exploring both benefits and challenges with a three-week mixed-methods data collection. Rigorously, an online survey questionnaire comprised questions on English reading materials and items assessing perceptions and challenges on ER using e-books, was administered to 135 undergraduate EFL students. Subsequently, semi-structured interviews were conducted via Zoom with 30 students, randomly selected from the survey participants, to provide deeper qualitative insights. Survey responses and interview data from undergraduate EFL students, primarily majoring in English Literature, revealed nuanced positive perceptions of ER using e-books. Beyond general convenience for reading in various settings, students specifically highlighted how features such as built-in dictionaries and adjustable font sizes directly facilitated their comprehension and reading fluency. Furthermore, the perceived environmental benefits contributed to a positive attitude towards digital reading. Analysis of the interview data further demonstrated how e-books supported more effective reading practices, with students reporting increased vocabulary acquisition through immediate dictionary access and improved comprehension through annotation tools. While acknowledging challenges such as eye strain, battery limitations, distractions, and internet dependency, this study demonstrates the tangible potential of strategically implemented e-books to enhance ER outcomes for Cambodian EFL undergraduates.

Keywords: *EFL Students, Electronic books, Extensive reading.*

Suggested citation: Thav, R., & Each, N. (2025). From Conventional to Technological Learning Experience: Cambodian Undergraduate EFL Students' Perceptions of Electronic Books on Extensive Reading Practices. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(4), 194-206. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(4).13

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

Extensive reading (ER) holds significant promise for language acquisition, as it allows learners to enhance their reading skills, expand vocabulary, and improve overall language proficiency (Nation & Waring, 2019). ER empowers students to read without relying on translation, grammar rules, or strategies, thereby facilitating the development of their foreign language abilities (Birketveit et al., 2018). This approach, implemented both in and outside the classroom, enables students to immerse themselves in accessible and engaging materials of their own choices (Aka, 2019). In today's digital age, it is essential to recognize that both electronic and printed books continue to play crucial roles as valuable sources of information (Budnyk et al., 2021).

In the Cambodian context, the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sport (MOEYS) has recognized the importance of reading by holding an annual nationwide event on March 11th to promote the joy and significance of reading, create a culture of lifelong learning, and celebrate the country's progress in improving reading outcomes. A few recent studies have investigated various aspects of English language reading in Cambodia, such as reading encouragement, reading comprehension, reading habits, and technology utilization for reading skills. For instance, one study focused on English language reading encouragement (Em et al., 2024), another examined English reading comprehension issues (Doung, 2019), while a third explored reading habits (Sun, 2018), and a study explored the perceptions of utilizing technology to enhance reading skills (Soeurn et al., 2024). However, research exploring the use of e-books and extensive reading within the Cambodian EFL context has not been found. To address this gap, the present study aims to explore Cambodian undergraduate EFL students' perceptions on extensive reading using e-books. Therefore, it seeks to address the following research questions:

1. To what extent do Cambodian EFL students perceive the use of e-books for extensive reading?
2. What challenges do Cambodian EFL students encounter while using e-books for extensive reading?

Literature Review

Extensive Reading (ER)

Extensive Reading (ER) can be defined as the reading of a large quantity of material for information or pleasure (Bamford & Day, 1997). In recent years, numerous studies have examined the linguistic benefits that ER can provide for students. These studies have demonstrated various positive outcomes, including improvements in reading fluency and comprehension (Iwata, 2022; McLean & Rouault, 2017), vocabulary acquisition (Liu & Zhang, 2018), writing ability (Azizi et al., 2020), and grammar knowledge (Lee et al., 2015).

Regarding reading fluency and comprehension, research has shown that engaging in ER can help students become more efficient and proficient readers. By exposing

themselves to a wide range of texts, students have the opportunity to practice and automatize their reading skills, leading to increased reading speed and better understanding of the materials (Iwata, 2022; McLean & Rouault, 2017). Similarly, ER was linked to the expansion of students' vocabulary, as they encounter new words and phrases in the texts they read (Liu & Zhang, 2018). Additionally, a study has found that ER can positively impact students' writing abilities, as the exposure to diverse language models and styles can enhance their own writing skills (Azizi et al., 2020). Furthermore, ER has been found to contribute to the development of students' grammatical knowledge. By reading extensively, students are able to internalize the patterns and structures of the language, leading to improved understanding and application of grammatical rules (Lee et al., 2015). In short, ER serves as a powerful tool for enhancing the overall development of language skills in students.

The Use of Electronic Books (e-books)

The use of e-books in language education has gained significant attention due to their versatility in digital reading across various electronic devices includes smartphones, tablets, computers, specialized e-book readers, and personal digital assistants (Yin & Hwang, 2018); (Zarzour et al., 2020). E-books offer several potential advantages over traditional paper textbooks (Zhang (2020). In particular, e-book reader hardware like the iPad, Kindle, and Nook provides a variety of features (such as still images, animated images, videos, audios, keyword searching, highlighting, note-taking, word definition, visual searching, bookmarks, and so on) to supplement traditional reading habits.

Furthermore, e-book reader devices include internet connectivity, allowing students to access additional information (e.g., other e-books, articles, videos, and photographs) to aid their comprehension and potentially improve their chances of learning success. Additionally, the environmental benefits of e-books have received limited attention, with only a few studies examining their potential for sustainable resource use and energy conservation (Moberg et al., 2011). There is a need for more comprehensive, interdisciplinary research that examines the various academic, technological, and environmental implications of integrating e-books into language learning contexts.

Previous Research Studies

The existing studies on the relationship between e-books and extensive reading have produced varied findings while some research has reported positive perceptions and experiences of students. The key findings from the last five years are summarized accordingly.

Mark and Bollen (2019) explored students' perceptions of ER through Xreading. The research combined a Student Survey conducted at the end of 2018 with an analysis of Xreading usage data, uncovering a contradiction in student experiences: while a substantial majority accessed Xreading through smartphones, their engagement remained low, as students averaged only 13.2 books and 5,724 words read over the semester—well below the 300,000-word benchmark generally linked to significant language acquisition benefits. While most participants reported ease in locating books and expressed enjoyment in using the platform, a substantial portion preferred physical books over digital formats, raising questions about the effectiveness of Xreading in fostering a genuine reading habit. Furthermore, despite students' assertions that Xreading enhanced their reading skills, vocabulary, grammar, and reading speed, the low engagement levels suggest that these perceptions may not reflect actual improvement. Alarmingly, only about half of the respondents indicated an intention

to continue using Xreading independently, underscoring the need for further research to objectively assess the platform's efficacy in promoting language acquisition.

Another study by Islami and Warni (2020) investigated EFL students' perception of e-book usage in their studies. The study involved EFL students predominantly aged 18-24, with a majority being female and located in East Jakarta. Participants were primarily in their fourth year, selected to capture similar experiences and concerns regarding e-books in educational contexts. Utilizing a quantitative survey method, the researchers employed an internet-based questionnaire on Google Forms consisting of 19 questions organized into three sections: demographic information, perceptions of e-books, and usage patterns. Data analysis revealed six key themes, including e-book use, awareness, and comparisons with printed books. Findings indicated that while EFL students generally expressed satisfaction with e-books, a preference for printed books emerged, with many using e-books primarily for research and reading for pleasure. Despite acknowledging the advantages of e-books, such as flexibility and convenience, students also highlighted significant drawbacks, including discomfort when reading on screens and challenges related to accessibility and availability in university libraries.

The next study from Bui and Macalister (2021), examined the effectiveness of extensive reading online (ERO) as an alternative approach to traditional ER in improving the reading fluency and attitudes towards reading of first-year university students in an EFL context. The research involved participants who had limited experience with extensive reading and an average vocabulary size of around 7,000-word families. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the researchers developed an online extensive reading program featuring graded books and required students to read a designated number of words each week over a ten-week period. Findings from the quantitative data indicated a notable increase in reading speed, while qualitative feedback revealed that many students held positive perceptions of ERO, appreciating its convenience and accessibility. However, some participants reported challenges such as eye strain and a limited variety of genres.

In addition, the study of Alafiyah (2023) focused on students' experiences using e-books for reading comprehension, involving four English language students at a university as participants. Using a qualitative approach, the researchers conducted interviews that were analyzed through thematic analysis of reading comprehension. Findings revealed that students had positive experiences with e-books, demonstrating an awareness of how factors such as the purpose of reading and the type of text influence their reading processes. They identified several advantages of e-books, including flexibility in access, ease of use, and increased engagement. However, students also highlighted drawbacks, such as technical distractions and eye strain from screen light. The study concludes that while e-books can effectively support reading comprehension in university contexts, it is essential to address the potential challenges they present.

Last but not least, the study of Ghafar (2024) lacks clarity regarding the specific number of participants, data collection methods, and findings related to a particular study. It appears that Ghafar is presenting a literature review on the use of e-books in education, particularly within the context of English Language Teaching (ELT), rather than reporting on a singular research study. The author indicates that literature analysis was utilized to explore e-books in ELT, employing logical explanations as a discussion strategy; however, there is no detailed account of the specific studies analyzed or the criteria for their selection. Instead of offering specific research findings, the study focuses on summarizing the advantages and disadvantages of e-books, highlighting

benefits such as portability, accessibility, and a positive impact on student motivation and engagement. It also acknowledges drawbacks, including eye strain, potential technical issues, the requirement for internet connectivity, and resistance from individuals accustomed to traditional printed materials.

Overall, the use of e-books has been recognized for its benefits and effectiveness in enhancing reading experiences (Alafiyah, 2023; Bui & Macalister, 2021; Ghafar, 2024; Islami & Warni, 2020; Mark & Bollen, 2019). However, issues such as eye strain and discomfort frequently arise when using e-books compared to traditional print books (Alafiyah, 2023; Islami & Warni, 2020).

Research Methods

Research Design

Mixed-method research was utilized to explore the students' perception of ER using e-books. This method involves collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and reporting both qualitative and quantitative data (Creswell, 2015). The quantitative method is used to examine the students' perception and challenges, which is learned about a particular group of students through measurement in numerical form. On the other hand, the qualitative method was used to discover the deep and clear information of students' perceptions and challenges in order to seek in-depth descriptions.

Population and Participants

205 undergraduate EFL students from one public university in north-west Cambodia constituted the entire population. From this population, a total of 135 students were selected using the Yamane formula $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ (Yamane, 1967). To ensure a representative sample, the researchers employed the Stratified Sampling Method, dividing the population into four distinct subgroups based on their academic year: first, second, third, and fourth year. The composition of each subgroup was as follows: (a) 96 first-year students, (b) 68 second-year students, (c) 20 third-year students, and (d) 21 fourth-year students.

135 target students participated in the survey questionnaire, while 30 students were selected for the interview. To ensure an accurate representation, the researchers categorized the population into four subgroups based on academic year (first year, second year, third year, and fourth year). The composition of each subgroup during the interview stage was as follows: (a) 64 first-year students, (b) 45 second-year students, (c) 13 third-year students, and (d) 14 fourth-year students. The table below provides detailed information about these students.

Table 1 shows the distribution of students participated by year of study. It provides a clear overview of the composition of each subgroup, highlighting the number of participants from each academic level.

Table 1. Target Students' Personal Information

	Categories	Frequencies	Percentages
Gender	Male	42	31.1%
	Female	93	68.9%
Age	17-18 years old	16	11.9%
	19-20 years old	62	45.9%
	21-22 years old	46	34.1%

	23-24 years old	11	8.1%
Enrolment Period (Academic Year of Study: 2021-2022)	First Year	64	47.4%
	Second Year	44	32.6%
	Third Year	13	9.6%
	Fourth Year	14	10.4%
English Language Learning Period	0-1 year	5	3.7%
	2-3 years	10	7.4%
	3-4 years	19	14.1%
	4-5 years	21	15.6%
	More than 5 years	80	59.3%

Research Instruments

There were two research instruments in the present study: survey questionnaire and semi-structured interview. The first instrument was a survey questionnaire adapted and modified from Smyth and Carlin (2012). The total number of questions was 28; they were divided into three parts, such as demographic information (5 items), students' perception of English reading materials (3 items) and students' perception and challenges on Extensive Reading using e-books (20 items). More importantly, the questions were designed in Google Form which is frequently used to quickly and easily construct surveys since it allows users to arrange events, ask questions, and collect a variety of data in a simple and efficient manner.

A semi-structured interview was employed as the second instrument, following the survey questionnaire, to gather insights into students' perceptions of the study. Four open-ended questions were designed to explore their experiences and challenges related to ER using e-books. These questions were developed by analyzing survey data, which revealed key themes and concerns that warranted further exploration. By encouraging participants to share their thoughts in detail, the interviews facilitated a deeper understanding of their perspectives. Conducted in a relaxed environment to promote comfort and openness, the recorded conversations were later transcribed for analysis, providing valuable insights into the challenges and benefits of using e-books for ER and enriching the overall findings of the study.

Data Collection

The quantitative and qualitative data for this study were collected over a three-week period from August to September 2022. In late August, the quantitative data was collected. The researchers conducted it through an online application, Telegram. First, a group of 135 target students was created via this platform. Then, the survey questionnaire link was delivered to the group. In addition to this, the questionnaires were described respectively, and it took less than 20 minutes to respond to the survey questionnaire. The first section was about the students' profiles and consisted of 5 items. Another 3 questions of English reading materials which asked students to answer in the second section. Moreover, 20 items of the third section which asked about students' perception as well as challenges on ER using e-books. In the first week of September, researchers started collecting the qualitative data through semi-structured interviews after implementing the survey questionnaire. The reason for doing the semi-structured interviews was in the purpose that students would give precise answers based on their experiences and each interview lasted from 10 to 15 minutes. Additionally, four questions were constructed, as well as the developing questions were suggested to gather insight and enrich the information. More importantly, Zoom Meeting was used, and the students were asked permission in order to record the video and audio during the interview process in order to be transcribed.

Data Analysis

Upon completing data collection, both quantitative and qualitative data were analyzed using specific procedures. First, the quantitative data collected through Google Forms was extracted to Microsoft Excel for cleaning. Once it was refined, this data was imported into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0 for descriptive statistical analysis, focusing on means and frequencies. Notably, an average mean score ranging from 3.51 to 4.50 indicated a significant level of agreement (Each & Suppasetserree, 2021). The significant level shows that students have positive perception ER using E-books. At the same time, the qualitative data collected was transcribed and analyzed using the Thematic Analysis approach. This approach involved identifying, analyzing, and reporting themes within the data, allowing for a detailed understanding of students' experiences, perceptions, and challenges. By coding the data into themes, key insights and trends emerged, providing a view of the challenges and benefits associated with ER using e-books.

Results

Questionnaire Result

Table 2 presents an analysis of student perceptions regarding Extensive Reading (ER) using e-books, revealing a strong consensus among students across all 20 items in the second part of the questionnaire, with an overall mean score of 3.77. This score clearly indicates that students possess a positive perception of ER through e-books. The mean scores for individual statements ranged from a high of $M=4.11$ to a low of $M=3.48$, demonstrating agreement.

The top three statements that received the highest ratings were: (1) "I think that being able to read English for enjoyment is important" ($M=4.11$); (2) "I learn new vocabularies when I read English for enjoyment" ($M=4.09$); and (3) "I would like to recommend others to use e-books" ($M=4.06$). These high mean scores reflect students' recognition of the significance of ER for personal enjoyment, their acknowledgment of its benefits in vocabulary acquisition, and their eagerness to recommend e-books to peers. The emphasis on enjoyment suggests that students view reading as a pleasurable activity that enhances their language skills, reinforcing the idea that motivation plays a crucial role in language learning.

Equally, the three statements with the lowest mean scores were: (1) "I also use e-books for lecture presentations" ($M=3.56$); (2) "I go to the bookstore looking for English materials for enjoyment" ($M=3.49$); and (3) "The notification of other applications distracts me when I use e-books" ($M=3.48$). These items received lower ratings, indicating some uncertainty among students regarding the utility of e-books for academic purposes, such as lecture presentations, as well as their habits in seeking English reading materials at bookstores. Additionally, the concern about distractions from notifications suggests that while e-books offer convenience, they also present challenges that may hinder the reading experience.

Despite these lower-rated items, they do not significantly impact the overall positive results of the study. The general trend indicates that Cambodian EFL students exhibit enthusiasm for using e-books and maintain a favorable view of ER through this medium. This positive perception underscores the potential of e-books as effective tools for enhancing language learning and engagement among students.

Table 2. Students' Perception on Extensive Reading Using Electronic Book

N ^o .	Statements	Means	Interpretation
1	In my free time, I like reading English for enjoyment.	3.76	Agree
2	I think that being able to read English for enjoyment is important.	4.11	Agree
3	I learn new vocabulary when I read English for enjoyment.	4.09	Agree
4	I am able to do writing tasks when I read English for enjoyment.	3.70	Agree
5	I improve my grammar through English reading for enjoyment.	3.84	Agree
6	I go to the bookstore looking for English reading materials for enjoyment.	3.49	Agree
7	I go to an online bookstore looking for English reading materials for enjoyment.	3.64	Agree
8	I read English materials on the internet for enjoyment.	3.83	Agree
9	I am aware that there are many available online platforms for users to get English E-books to read.	3.76	Agree
10	I feel happy to use E-books for enjoyment reading.	3.77	Agree
11	I also use E-books for lecture presentation.	3.56	Agree
12	I use E-books for doing research too.	3.81	Agree
13	Highlighting function on E-books makes it easy for me to notice the important messages of the text.	3.73	Agree
14	The Font Size Changing function on E-books makes it easy to read the text when I want big or small size.	3.79	Agree
15	Color Changing Function on E-books makes my eyes stay focused on the reading text.	3.69	Agree
16	Well-Organized Interface makes it easy to read the text on E-books.	3.73	Agree
17	The Search function on E-books makes it easy to look for the sections I want.	3.81	Agree
18	The Saved Page function on E-books makes it easy to continue what I should read later.	3.94	Agree
19	The notification of the other applications distracts me when I use E-books.	3.48	Agree
20	I would like to recommend others to use E-books.	4.06	Agree
Overall		3.77	Positive Opinion

Semi-structured Interview Result

The findings from semi-structured interviews emerged four key themes from the analysis such as English language learning skills improvement, perceptions of user usefulness, students' recommendations, and problems encountered while using e-books.

English Language Skills Improvement

All students (N=30) stated several advantages of using e-books, such as improvements in reading rate and comprehension, vocabulary, writing ability, and grammar, as shown in the examples in the following quotes.

Student 7, "Yes, it is really important. Because an activity such as reading books in your free time doesn't mean wasting your time without getting back some benefits. Despite this, it gives us such a great writing ability that is really important with the grammar, and also includes more vocabulary, knowledge, and gives you greater self-confidence as a reader."

Student 28, “After I read the books that I favor during my free time, I found that it provides me many benefits. I feel so relaxed and obtain to find out new words from the books. Moreover, I understand more about grammar structure likewise because of the author’s writing. In short, I learn to use the sentences and produce the words correctly in my writing and speaking.”

User Usefulness

Using e-books is considered to provide benefits with user-friendly functions, according to the 30 students who participated in the interview. The examples are quoted below.

Student 21, “I totally agree that e-book is good to use. Because there is a dictionary, font size changing function, bright or dark mode, searching function, etc.”

Student 23, “Using e-books is very important. I am able to do many things in one device such as highlighting, note, bookmark, dictionary, keyword searching. Most of the books are free. So that I can save my money too.”

Students’ Recommendations

All students (N=30) recommended others to use e-books for reading as the following quotes:

Student 6, “It is highly recommended for use unless you have a high concentration. Sometimes, the notification of other applications distracts us while we concentrate on reading the text. However, if you have high concentration on what you are doing, an e-book is a very good platform for reading according to its useful functions.”

Student 21, “E-book is highly recommended for some reasons, such as saving money, space, and the environment and there are many useful functions in e-books, which are dictionaries, saved last page visited, and font size which user can set to make them feel easy while reading.”

Problem Encounter while Using Electronic Books (E-books)

According to the interview, 11 students mentioned a common problem while using e-books which is eye strain, the other 5 students mentioned the device battery, other 4 students mentioned notification distraction, and the other 4 students raised the internet connection as the problem as seen in the following quotes:

Student 25, “The internet connection in my location is the issue when reading e-books. I can obtain the books I require unless I am in a location with a reliable internet connection.”

Student 26, “Issues I have with reading electronic books, such as eye fatigue, notification distraction, and device battery.”

Discussion

This study examined how Cambodian EFL students perceive extensive reading with e-books, highlighting its significance in supporting their academic pursuits. The study found that Cambodian students had a positive perception with an average mean score (M = 3.77), indicating their favorable view of using e-books for both leisure reading and improving English language skills. More importantly, the findings emphasize how ER significantly benefits students in conquering core aspects of the English language. Thus, encouraging students to read more extensively based on their interests should be prioritized by teachers and schools. The reasons that contribute to students' positive perception of ER using e-books are stated in the following paragraphs.

The first reason is that ER enhances English language skills. Previous studies have demonstrated significant improvements in specific areas of language learning, including enhancing reading fluency and comprehension skills (Iwata, 2022; McLean & Rouault, 2017), increased vocabulary acquisition rates (Liu & Zhang, 2018), advancements in writing ability (Azizi et al., 2020; Mermelstein, 2015; Park, 2016), and a deeper understanding of grammar rules (Lee et al., 2015).

The second reason is the functions of e-books, which is highly useful for students. E-books offer various functionalities such as keyword searching, highlighting, note adding, word adding, visual searching bookmarks, and saved last visited page (Zarzour et al., 2020). This research discovered that e-books are capable of containing numerous documents within a single device, saving both resources and the environment. Thus, students benefit from the ability to access e-books anytime and anywhere as shown in the study of Islami and Warni (2020), where students expressed satisfaction with the flexible accessibility, convenience, speed, ease of use, and usefulness of available features. To sum up, this functionality enhances the learning experience, as it promotes active engagement and encourages deeper understanding of the content.

The third reason, students highly recommended e-books is their enjoyable reading experience, attribute to several beneficial features. E-books are space-saving, allowing students to carry an entire library in a single device. The days of carrying heavy backpacks filled with textbooks are over, as e-books provide a convenient and lightweight alternative. E-books save students' time for students; with just a few clicks, they can instantly access a huge range of resources without the need to search through physical shelves or wait for books to be delivered. Moreover, e-books are cost-saving. Traditional print books can be expensive, especially when students need multiple copies or updated editions. In contrast, e-books are generally more affordable, as they eliminate production and distribution costs. This cost-effectiveness is particularly beneficial for students on tight budgets as noted in the study of Buckley and Tritt (2011).

The fourth reason highlighted by students is the positive environmental impact of reading e-books, as demonstrated in the study by (Moberg et al., 2011). By choosing for electronic formats, they actively contribute to the preservation of trees and help reduce their carbon footprint. This eco-friendly aspect of e-books not only enhances their appeal but resonates with environmentally conscious individuals who value sustainability and care for the planet.

On the other hands, despite these advantages, the challenges arise when using e-books. One significant challenge is eye strain, as highlighted in a study conducted by Islami and Warni (2020) and Alafiyah (2023). The research indicated that students faced difficulties using e-books for extended periods due to this issue. As a result, some students prefer print-based materials that do not cause the same level of eye strain. Another common challenge associated with e-books is involves technological issues, such as battery life, distractions from notifications, and internet connectivity problems, which have been identified as obstacles to effective e-books usage.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that EFL students generally perceive extensive reading using e-books positively, by a total mean score of 3.77 in terms of convenience and accessibility of e-books, along with their interactive feature multimedia elements,

contributing to an advanced reading experience and increased motivation to read in English and contribute to environmental preservation. However, the students addressed the challenges related to eye strain, device battery, digital distractions, and internet connection while using e-books. In today's digital era, e-books provide learners or readers with the flexibility to engage in reading activities both inside and outside the classroom. In light of the study's outcomes and conclusions, the researchers put forward the following recommendations:

1. Educational institutions should adjust their reading curricula and actively encourage students to embrace the use of e-books due to their convenience and user-friendliness.
2. Teachers should integrate the concept of e-books into learning activities to enhance not only reading skills but also other English language skills and other academic subjects.
3. Students should have self-sufficiency to explore their preferred reading materials according to their proficiency levels.
4. Researchers should further explore the impact of e-books on students' critical thinking skills, digital literacy, and overall academic performance.

Acknowledgement

This manuscript owes its completion to the invaluable contribution of the EFL students and the facilitation of the English Department facilitators. Their active participation and steady dedication have been crucial in shaping the outcome of this study. We express our sincerest gratitude to each and every one of them for their irreplaceable support. Furthermore, we extend our heartfelt appreciation to all of the reviewers who provided their insightful comments and constructive feedback during the preparation of this manuscript. Their expertise and evaluation have significantly enhanced the quality and clarity of this study. Their valuable suggestions have not only contributed to this manuscript but will also serve as a valuable guide for future research activities.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Aka, N. (2019). Reading performance of Japanese high school learners following a one-year extensive reading program. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 31(1), 1–18.
- Alafiyah, T. (2023). *Students' experiences of using E-books in reading comprehension* [Undergraduate thesis, UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan]. Etheses UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. <http://etheses.uingusdur.ac.id/6593/>
- Azizi, M., Tkáčová, H., Pavlíková, M., & Jenisová, Z. (2020). Extensive reading and the writing ability of EFL learners: The effect of group work. *European Journal of Contemporary Education*, 9(4), 726–739.
- Bamford, J., & Day, R. R. (1997). Extensive reading: What is it? Why bother? *Language Teacher–Kyoto-JALT*, 21, 6–8.

- Birketveit, A., Rimmereide, H. E., Bader, M., & Fisher, L. (2018). Extensive reading in primary school EFL. *Acta Didactica Norge*. <https://doi.org/10.5617/adno.5643>
- Buckley, M., & Tritt, D. (2011). Ebook approval plans: Integration to meet user needs. *Computers in Libraries*, 31(3), 15–18.
- Budnyk, O., Kachak, T., Blyznyuk, T., Rostykus, N., & Boiko, H. (2021). Printed and e-book: Problems of choice of modern students of the university. *Revista Tempos e Espaços em Educação*, 14(33), e15913.
- Bui, T., & Macalister, J. (2021). Online extensive reading in an EFL context: Investigating reading fluency and perceptions. *System*, 93, Article 102318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2020.102318>
- Creswell, J. W. (2015). Revisiting mixed methods and advancing scientific practices. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 9(2), 122–126. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689815572012>
- Doung, D. (2019). Investigating English reading comprehension problems of Cambodian high school students. *American International Journal of Social Science*, 8(3), 52–56.
- Each, N., & Suppasetsee, S. (2021). The effects of mobile-blended cooperative learning on EFL students' listening comprehension in Cambodian context. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 14(2), 143–170.
- Em, S., Chau, L., Ros, R., Dy, P., & Pen, D. (2024). Encouraging English language reading in Cambodia: A case study of Takeo provincial higher educational institutions. *Journal of General Education and Humanities*, 3(2), 85–101. <https://doi.org/10.58421/gehu.v3i2.205>
- Ghafar, Z. (2024). The impact of electronic books on learning English language in the digital era: An overview. *Digital Learning and Distance Education*, 2(7), 635–644.
- Islami, J. D., & Warni, S. (2020). EFL students' perceptions of reading electronic books. *Journal of ELT Research*, 5(1), 37–52.
- Iwata, A. (2022). The effectiveness of extensive reading (ER) on the development of EFL learners' sight vocabulary size and reading fluency. *The Reading Matrix: An International Online Journal*, 22(2), 74–91.
- Lee, J., Schallert, D. L., & Kim, E. (2015). Effects of extensive reading and translation activities on grammar knowledge and attitudes for EFL adolescents. *System*, 52, 38–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2015.04.016>
- Liu, J., & Zhang, J. (2018). The effects of extensive reading on English vocabulary learning: A meta-analysis. *English Language Teaching*, 11(6), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v11n6p1>
- Mark, H., & Bollen, D. (2019). Student perceptions of an online extensive reading platform. *崇城大学紀要 (Sōjō University Bulletin)*, 44, 145–152.
- McLean, S., & Rouault, G. (2017). The effectiveness and efficiency of extensive reading at developing reading rates. *System*, 70, 92–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2017.09.009>
- Mermelstein, A. D. (2015). Improving EFL learners' writing through enhanced extensive reading. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 27(2), 182–198. <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1078420>

- Moberg, Å., Borggren, C., & Finnveden, G. (2011). Books from an environmental perspective—Part 2: E-books as an alternative to paper books. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 16, 238–246. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-011-0275-4>
- Nation, I. S. P., & Waring, R. (2019). *Teaching extensive reading in another language*. Routledge.
- Park, J. (2016). Integrating reading and writing through extensive reading. *ELT Journal*, 70(3), 287–295. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccv049>
- Smyth, S., & Carlin, A. P. (2012). Use and perception of ebooks in the University of Ulster: A case study. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 18(2), 176–205. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13614533.2012.719851>
- Soeurn, C., Ly, S., & Vann, R. (2024). Students' perceptions toward utilizing technology to help reading skills: A case study of IFL students in one public university in Battambang. *Journal of English for Specific Purposes in Indonesia*, 3(2), 104–114.
- Sun, S. (2018). Reading habits and academic performance: A study of university students in Cambodia. *UC Occasional Paper Series*, 3(1).
- Yamane, T. (1967). *Statistics: An introductory analysis* (2nd ed.). Harper & Row.
- Yin, C., & Hwang, G.-J. (2018). Roles and strategies of learning analytics in the e-publication era. *Knowledge Management & E-Learning*, 10(4), 455–468.
- Zarzour, H., Bendjaballah, S., & Harirche, H. (2020). Exploring the behavioral patterns of students learning with a Facebook-based e-book approach. *Computers & Education*, 156, Article 103957. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103957>
- Zhang, M. (2020). Rational actions or institutional actions: A study on the rationality in academic librarians' decision-making processes when purchasing e-book products. *Library & Information Science Research*, 42(2), 101018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2020.101018>

